

Glutathione Reductase (GR) Activity Assay Kit Instruction

(Catalog #A062; 50T for 48 samples)

I. The significance of determination:

Glutathione Reductase (GR) is a flavin enzyme, also known as flavin protein, which contains one molecule flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) as a coenzyme. When it participates in *in vivo* reactions, coenzyme NADPH can provide hydrogen ions, oxidized glutathione (GSSG) can be catalytically reduced to glutathione (GSH). GSH can make enzyme-containing thiol (-SH) in the reduced and active state, maintaining the integrity of the erythrocyte membrane, to prevent the oxidation of hemoglobin.

GR are localized in the cytosol and microsomes part. GR are widespread in the tissue cells of various organs, thus play a pivotal role in redox reactions in living organisms.

II. The principle of determination:

In the case of the presence of GR and hydrogen ions provided by NADPH, GSSG is catalytically reduced to GSH, resulting in GSH increase and NADPH decrease.

The reaction formula as follows: $GSSG + NADPH + H^+ \xrightarrow{GR} 2GSH + NADP^+$

We can calculate the GR activity by detecting the change of NADPH absorbance values at 340nm.

III. Kit contents (50T for 48 samples)

Reagent I: 60ml × 2 bottles, 4°C for 3 months.

Reagent II: powder × 4 tubes, 4°C for 6 months; add 1ml double distilled water each tube when using after fully dissolved for later use, 4°C preservation.

Reagent III: powder × 2 tubes, 4°C for 3 months; add 1ml double distilled water each tube when using after fully dissolved for later use, -20°C preservation.

Preparation of working solution: formulate in accordance with the proportion of Reagent I: II: III= 2300: 60: 30, use immediately after preparation is completed, the remaining stored at 4°C for 4~5 days.

IV. Determination of GR activity in serum (plasma)

1、Serum (plasma) samples pre-processing:

Serum does not require centrifugation; plasma needs to centrifuge at 2000 ~ 3000 rpm/min for 8 minutes.

2、The operational processes of GR activity assay of serum (plasma):

① Adjust to a wavelength of 340nm on the UV spectrophotometer, using a 1cm light path quartz cuvette with double distilled water to zero setting (prepare two quartz cuvettes, one for zero setting, another for assay).

② Add 50μl fresh serum (plasma) to the corresponding numbered tubes, then draw 2.4ml working solution into the tubes, rapid mixing and timing.

③ Pour rapidly into a quartz cuvette, read the absorbance value at 30 seconds, record as A_1 .

④Re-pour this colorimetric solution into the original test tube, react in a 37°C water bath pot for two minutes accurately, then quickly pour into a quartz cuvette, read the absorbance value at 2 minute 30 seconds, record as A₂.

⑤Calculate the difference of the absorbance values between the two times.

[Note]: 1、 You can only do one tube when operate.

2、 Quartz cuvette is best to pre-warm, take a small beaker and add a certain amount of double distilled water (the liquid level should not be too 2/3 of the cuvette height), place in 37°C water bath pot, in the course of the reaction, the cuvette can be placed in the beaker so that it's temperature maintaining at 37°C (Because NADPH test is greatly affected by temperature).

3、 Two people is best needed to do this experiment, one record time, another do experiment, so you can ensure the accuracy of the experimental results.

3、 Calculation of GR activity unit in serum (plasma):

①The definition of GR activity unit in serum(plasma):

One unit is the amount of enzyme that will change 1mM concentration of substrate NADPH in the reaction system per minute in per liter of serum (plasma).

②The formula:

$$\text{血清(浆)中GR活力}(U/L) = \frac{(A_1 - A_2)}{6.22 * \text{比色光径}(1\text{cm})} \div \frac{\text{反应时间}}{(2\text{分钟})} \times \frac{1000(\text{ml})}{\text{取样量}(0.05\text{ml})}$$

* 6.22 is the extinction coefficient of 1mM NADPH at 340nm wavelength of 1cm optical path.

V. Determiration of GR activity in tissue homogenates

1、 Tissue samples pre-processing:

Accurately weigh tissue weight, add normal saline according to the proportion of weight (g): volume (ml) = 1: 9, Use a mechanical homogenizer under ice water bath to prepare a 10% tissue homogenate, then centrifuge at 2500 rpm/min for 10 minutes, and the supernatant is tested.

2、 The operational processes of GR activity assay of tissue:

①Adjust to a wavelength of 340nm on the UV spectrophotometer, using a 1cm light path quartz cuvette with double distilled water to zero setting (prepare two quartz cuvettes, one for zero setting, another for assay).

②Add 20μl tissue homogenate to the corresponding numbered tubes, then draw 2.4ml working solution into the tubes, rapid mixing and timing.

③Pour rapidly into a quartz cuvette, read the absorbance value at 30 seconds, record as A₁.

④Re-pour this colorimetric solution into the original test tube, react in a 37°C water bath pot for two minutes accurately, then quickly pour into a quartz cuvette, read the absorbance value at 2 minute 30 seconds, record as A₂.

⑤Calculate the difference of the absorbance values between the two times.

[Note]: 1、 You can only do one tube when operate.

2、 Quartz cuvette is best to pre-warm, take a small beaker and add a certain amount of double distilled water (the liquid level should not be too 2/3 of the cuvette height), place in 37°C water bath pot, in the course of the reaction, the cuvette can be placed in the beaker so that it's temperature maintaining at 37°C (Because NADPH test is greatly affected by temperature).

3、 Two people is best needed to do this experiment, one record time, another do experiment, so you can ensure the accuracy of the experimental results.

3、 Calculation of GR activity unit in tissue homogenates:

①The definition of GR activity unit in tissue homogenates:

One unit is the amount of enzyme that will change 1mM concentration of substrate NADPH in the reaction system per minute in per gram of tissue protein.

②The formula:

$$\text{组织中 GR活力} \quad (U / gprot) = \frac{(A1 - A2)}{6.22 * \times \text{比色光径} (1cm)} \div \frac{\text{反应时间}}{(2\text{分钟})} \div \left[\frac{\text{取样量}}{(ml)} \times \frac{\text{待测样本蛋白浓度}}{(gprot / ml)} \right] \times \frac{\text{样本测定前}}{\text{稀释倍数}}$$

* 6.22 is the extinction coefficient of 1mM NADPH at 340nm wavelength of 1cm optical path.